

WATER QUALITY MONITORING PROTOTYPE FOR FISH FARMING USING LORA NETWORK

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Summary -Technological advances in monitoring the management of water resource use and environmental recovery have contributed to maintaining the integrity of natural resources. The objective of the work was to develop a prototype for monitoring parameters such as temperature, dissolved oxygen, pH, and water turbidity, which qualify water in its nutritional and sustainable aspects. We conducted tests in a lagoon in Santos-SP, and the developed system proved effective, contributing to sustainability in fish farming.

Key words: IoT; LoRa; Monitoring; Pisciculture; Productivity

INTRODUCTION

According to [2], different areas have highlighted the benefits that automation technologies have brought to society; with more accurate information and this knowledge, companies become more assertive, increasing productivity and gaining competitiveness. Technological innovation has become an extremely relevant indicator for the substantial growth of agriculture, working in an interdisciplinary way and using technology to help solve real problems.

The future of technology and process automation are directly related to the Internet of Things (IoT), which refers to the constantly evolving technology that connects real-world objects to people to make their lives more accessible [3]. This concept is increasingly used in agriculture to connect sensors to farmers and facilitate decision-making in the production process [4] [1].

Therefore, this study proposes the development of a water quality monitoring prototype, using sensors connected to a microcontroller to collect data and communication networks with the LoRa protocol to make information available in cloud systems, facilitating management and control.

A buoy was assembled to support what involves temperature, dissolved oxygen, pH, and turbidity sensors used to collect data and sent to the cloud for subsequent analysis and decision-making.

The general objective of this work was to develop a system for monitoring water quality in fish farming, making information available online to producers. The project's specific objectives were to create a monitoring system to measure water quality using dissolved oxygen (DO), temperature, pH, and water turbidity sensors and to develop the presentation of monitored information in the form of a dashboard (graphics) made available on mobile devices.

Due to increased demand for fish and investments in the production sector, this study aims to help small and medium-sized fish producers increase quality production and reduce environmental impacts on the water.

DEVELOPMENT

The water quality monitoring system for fish farming using the LoRa network for 915MHz (standard for Brazil) has a microcontroller and a radio for data communication tests sent over the network, shown in Fig.1, where the OLED display shows the received temperature and turbidity data and the RSSI signal strength of -110 dBm.

Figure 1 – Network test with microcontroller
Source: The Authors (2023)

The microcontroller was configured as a gateway for network tests, receiving and sending data to the cloud via the Wi-Fi network. The gateway is installed in a location with an Internet router so that the data collected by the Lora network is sent to the cloud, as shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2 – Gateway in the network test
Source: The Authors (2023).

Fig. 3 shows the prototype for data collection with temperature transmission at a point in Morro da Campina, 1 km from the gateway shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 3 – Prototype communication test with the gateway
 Source: The Authors (2023).

Fig. 4 shows the map of Enseada beach in the city of Guarujá, on the coast of São Paulo. The gateway was installed at point G on the map, and with the battery-powered prototype, 5 points were covered for communication tests at each point. Communication was tested to check the signal quality and the data packet's transmission.

Figure 4 – LoRa Network test map
 Source: The Authors (2023).

Table 1 describes the locations of the communication test points, the strength of the signals received by the gateway, and the distance from the points to the gateway.

Table 1 – Network test signals

Points	Location	Signal Strength (dBm)	Distance (m)
A	Campina Hill	-101	1000
B	Horacio Lafer Square	-108	566
W	Casa Grande Hotel	-116	821
D	Center Castilho	-116	563
AND	Women's Health Center	-71	191

Source: The Authors (2023).

pH SENSOR CALIBRATION

The pH sensor is calibrated according to the manufacturer's recommendation, and it is necessary to place the probe in the pH solution with a value of 7.0, as shown in Fig. 5, marking the pH voltage value plotted on the serial port, which in this case was found in 1930.

Figure 5 – Calibration of the pH 7.0 sensor
 Source: The Authors (2023).

After calibration, drying, and cleaning with distilled water, the probe was immersed in a solution with pH 4.0, as shown in Fig. 6. It displayed the pH voltage value on the serial monitor. During this calibration, the value found was 1415. was re-recorded. During this calibration, the value found was 1415.

Figure 6 – Calibration of the pH 4.0 sensor
 Source: The Authors (2023).

FINAL TEST

The system efficiency tests were carried out under conditions closer to the reality proposed in this work. Sensor data was collected at Lagoa da Saudade in Santos, São Paulo, Brazil, with the location shown in Fig. 7.

Figure 7 – Location of Lagoa da Saudade, Santos - SP
 Source: Google Maps (2023)

With a clear sky, few clouds, and wind, the test was conducted on May 28, 2023, between 10 a.m. and 12 p.m. The gateway and prototype were positioned according to the map in Fig. 8 to compare signal strength data.

Figure 8 – Map with the layout of the gateway and prototype
 Source: The Authors (2023)

Fig. 9 shows the gateway (point in yellow) installed at the point with coordinates latitude - 23.948939036434528° and longitude - 46.35115221926869°, in Santos - SP.

Figure 9 – Gateway position
 Source: The Authors (2023)

The prototype was installed on a buoy to float in the lagoon and the coordinate position with latitude of -23.948125557644897° and longitude of -46.35434906720823°, as shown in Fig. 10.

Figure 10 – Prototype with the buoy.
 Source: The Authors (2023)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The ThingSpeak platform is used for testing and implementing IoT projects, integrating Matlab software, and providing information via the Web.

In addition, it has several tools, such as graphs for data visualization and triggers for automating tasks.

The results obtained through the four measurements made using the Turbidity, PH, Temperature, and Dissolved Oxygen sensors are shown in Fig. 11.

The measurement results showed that the data followed a normal distribution. The dot discrepancies in the samples are due to adjustments in the positioning of the buoy with the prototype in the lagoon.

Figure 11 – Graph with points received from sensor measurements
 Source: The Authors (2023)

Fig. 12 shows the graph of measurements from the four sensors presented with averages of the results collected every 10 minutes.

Figure 12 – Graph with points received from sensor measurements with filter
 Source: The Authors (2023)

Fig. 13 shows the signal strength received during the tests. The data received by the ThingSpeak platform had a reception efficiency of 96%.

Figure 13 – Received signal strength graph.
 Source: The Authors (2023)

To ensure water quality on an aquaculture farm, it is essential to regularly monitor water quality and take measures to keep the water clean and safe for fish. This study focused on developing a water quality monitoring prototype using the LoRa network, which could measure temperature, pH, dissolved oxygen, and water turbidity.

The water quality monitoring system for fish farming using the LoRa network presented satisfactory results for improving tank management, mainly due to its agility and low acquisition cost components, which facilitate its implementation.

The use of LoRa technology allowed long-range communication, with results obtained in line with expectations, and this enables the coverage of large geographic areas with less network infrastructure, low energy consumption, and operating for long periods, and with the scalability to add and easily remove devices according to project needs.

The level of accuracy in measurements was higher than expected, even with the sensors being on a buoy with constant changes in inclination, direction, and vibrations.

Monitoring the data collected and stored on the ThingSpeak platform gave the user information to easily monitor sensor data through a mobile device or even a notebook.

As future perspectives for improvements, the development of boards for installing electronic

components, weight, and size reduction, advances in the buoyancy system with more excellent protection and stability, and the development of new functionalities in the presentation of collected data and comparison with quality parameters.

Monitoring water quality in fish farming using the developed prototype will reduce the risk of contamination of tanks and the chemical and physical quality of the sustainable environment for fish health, thus increasing fish productivity and quality. Raised in nurseries.

The prototype developed for fish farming can be applied in several other areas, changing the specific sensors for the application and the dashboard to make information available to the user.

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